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**BURNOUT AMONG TEACHER EDUCATORS
OF GRANT-IN-AID INSTITUTIONS IN RELATION TO THEIR
PERCEPTION OF INSTITUTIONAL CLIMATE**

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ABSTRACT:

This research paper deals with the burnout in teacher educators in relation to the institutional climate. The results of this study are based on the survey of 46 teacher educators of Grant-in-Aid institutions associated to University of Lucknow (including Department of Education, University of Lucknow). The level of burnout has been measured by Maslach Burnout Inventory (Educators Survey). The institutional climate has been assessed using a self-constructed Institutional Climate Scale. The results of the study indicate that there does not exist any relationship between burnout in teacher educators and institutional climate of the institutions they are serving with.

Keywords: Burnout, Institutional Climate, Teacher-educator, Grant-in-aid institution.

INTRODUCTION:

Burnout probably has always been a problem in the human service professions but various social and political changes in the world have made people more aware of the problem now. Earlier burnout was a hidden problem because, until recently, professionals had multiple options for dealing with their developing exhaustion (Paine, 1984). Though stress was always present but more people in the past were part of a larger social community that helped them to comprehend and accept stress. This closeness of individuals with the society helped to alleviate stress, reduce strain and burnout (Cherniss, 1980).

Burnout is a syndrome of emotional exhaustion, depersonalisation and reduced personal accomplishment that can occur among individuals who do 'people work' of some kind Maslach (1984). The term burnout was introduced by Freudenberger to describe the later stage of negative process of experiencing continued stress (Dixit, 1992). Carroll & White (1984) defined burnout as a construct used to explain observable decrement in the typical quality and quantity of work performed by a person on the job. Cherniss (1980) refers burnout as a particular kind of response on job- the tendency to treat clients in a detached mechanical fashion.

The burnout syndrome is of wide spread in teachers (Sahu, 1992; Lau, 2002;

Cunningham, 2004; Denton, 2009; Durr, 2009; Tucker, 2009). It is often said that teaching is one of the noble professions but the realities of classroom life and institutional environment have made teaching a stressful profession. As a result many teachers are experiencing that their feelings about themselves, their students and their profession are becoming negative than they were initially. Such teachers do not derive any pleasure from teaching; rather they take it as a routine work. For them, teaching is no more a source of satisfaction. This develops among them a sense of frustration, loss of enthusiasm and alienation from job. These teachers are susceptible to developing chronic feelings of emotional exhaustion and fatigue, negative attitude towards their students and a loss of feeling of accomplishment on the job (Trivedi 2005). Singh (1997) defines teacher burnout as, "A stress reaction to the pressures and routines of a teacher's assignment. It may be manifested by physical (fatigue, sleeplessness), psychological (moodiness, irritability) and attitudinal symptoms (decreased caring for students).

Dimensions of Burnout

The burnout has three dimensions. The most agreed dimension is exhaustion-wearing out, loss of energy, depletion, debilitation and fatigue. Although sometimes this exhaustion is a physical one, more often a psychological or emotional exhaustion is central to burnout. The second dimension is a negative shift in response to others i.e. depersonalisation. It is manifested as negative or inappropriate attitude towards clients, loss of idealism and irritability. The third dimension of burnout is negative response towards oneself and one's personal accomplishments, also termed as depression, low morale, withdrawal, reduced productivity or capability.

Symptoms of Burnout

Burnout affects the whole person. It affects all the aspects of the person; intellect, feelings, relationships, spirit, physical health as well as job performance. There seems a general consensus that the symptoms of burnout include attitudinal, emotional and physical components. Symptoms of burnout may be summarised as: emotional stress (manifested as anxiety, irritability, sadness or low self-esteem), high resistance to going to work every day, noticeably less idealistic, feeling tired and exhausted all day, cynical towards clients, blaming clients or students for their own difficulties, labelling clients in derogatory terms, often late or absent from duty, a sense of failure, deterioration in performance at work, psychosomatic problems (insomnia, ulcers, headaches, fatigue, high blood pressure), increased marital and family conflicts, anger and resentment, discouragement and indifference, isolation and withdrawal, postponing client or student contacts, inability to concentrate on or listen to what student is saying, increasingly 'going by the book', avoiding discussion of work with colleagues, self-preoccupation, rigidity in thinking and resistance to change, excessive use of alcohols, loss of positive feeling towards clients or students, stereotyping of students etc.

Institutional Climate

In modern society most people spend their working life in an organisation of some

kind and therefore they have first-hand experience of organisational life (Robertson & Cooper, 1983). Academic institutions are one of these organisations. Institutional climate is the perceived and experienced attributes of an institution. The institutional climate may be pictured as a personality sketch of the institution, as personality describes an individual, so climate defines the essence of an institution (Sharma, 1982). Institutional climate is defined as a set of measurable properties of the work environment, perceived directly or indirectly by the people who live and work in that environment, which influences their motivation. Institutional climate is the phenomenon that represents interaction between personal and organisational characteristics. The common characteristics of the institutional climate are:

1. Institutional climate is a multi-faceted phenomenon.
2. Though subject to change, institutional climate is enduring over time.
3. Despite time difference in individual perceptions, there can be broad overall agreement in describing institutional climate.
4. When used in the form of summated averaged perceptions of individuals, institution climate is a characteristic of the institution instead of the individual.
5. Institutional climate influences the behaviour of members of the institution.

Burnout and Institutional Climate

The work environment plays an important role in promoting or preventing burnout (Pines, 1984). Factors contributing to burnout in human service programmes can be found at three different levels of analysis: the individual, the work setting and the larger culture & society (Cherniss, 1980). Among these the work setting is most important. The primary sources of burnout in the work setting are the organisational design, leadership & supervision and social interaction among staff. These factors are interrelated. The relationships among people have a critical effect on job stress and burnout. Healthy Social interaction among colleagues in an institution can help reduce job stress and burnout.

The influence of the external environment on the work setting can't be overlooked. The nature of the community served by an institution has a strong impact on those aspects of the work setting that influence burnout. The relationships between the educational institutions and other community organisations also influence burnout among staff. Physical qualities of work environment also have major impact on people's mental and physical health. A comfortable work environment is negatively correlated with burnout (Pines, 1984).

The social dimension of the work environment includes all the people coming in direct contact with the individual as part of his or her work. Service recipients, customers, clients, students, co-workers, supervisors, administrators, all affect the social dimension. The social dimension of the work environment also affects job burnout. If the social environment is very supportive burnout may not occur, even if the work itself is extremely stressful. The organisational dimensions of the work environment that affect job burnout include bureaucratic hassles, administrative features and role of the individual in the orga-

nization. The problems mentioned most often as burnout-causing in the organisational dimension include red tape, too much paper work, communication problems, rigid hierarchy, excessive rules and regulations. The more senseless the rules and regulations and the more arbitrary the policy influences, the more job burnout. Pines (1984) found that high degrees of administrative interference were correlated with high degrees of burnout.

NEED OF THE STUDY:

It is often said that people enter the teaching profession with hope, enthusiasm and vigour but something either in system of education or the environment of teacher education institutions reduces their interest and produce psychologically unfavourable attitude towards their profession. The working conditions may be one of the possible cause of this undesirable change in the attitude and performance of teachers. If a teacher is feeling stressed on his job, he can't do best in his profession.

This study is an attempt to have a sincere look on job related burnout among teacher educators of grant-in-aid institutions in relation to the institutional climate. As burnout among teacher educators and institutional climate in teacher education institutions associated to University of Lucknow has not been studied earlier, the present investigation is focussed on teacher educators of grant-in-aid institutions associated to University of Lucknow.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

To find out the relationship between institutional climate and burnout among teacher-educators in grant-in-aid institutions.

NULL HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY:

There is no significant relationship between burnout among teacher educators of grant-in-aid institutions and institutional climate.

Based on this null hypothesis, three sub-hypotheses have been formulated corresponding to three dimensions of burnout.

Sub-Null hypotheses:

Ho₁ : There is no significant relationship between emotional exhaustion dimension of burnout among teacher educators of grant-in-aid institutions and institutional climate of these institutions.

Ho₂ : There is no significant relationship between depersonalisation dimension of burnout among teacher educators of grant-in-aid institutions and institutional climate of these institutions.

Ho₃ : There is no significant relationship between reduced personal accomplishment dimension of burnout among teacher educators of grant-in-aid institutions and institutional climate of these institutions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

This study belongs to the category of descriptive research. The survey method was adopted in this study.

POPULATION AND SAMPLE:

The teacher educators teaching in B. Ed. and/or M.Ed. course in Education Department of University of Lucknow and colleges associated to University of Lucknow constitute the population of the study. A sample of 46 teacher educators (37 female and 9 male) was selected by purposive sampling.

TOOLS USED:

Maslach Burnout Inventory-Educators Survey (MBI-Educators Form) was used to collect data about burnout among teacher educators and self-made Institutional Climate Scale was administered to assess the teacher educators' perception of institutional climate of the institution. The reliability of Institutional Climate Scale is 0.97 as established by spilt-half method. The Institutional climate Scale has content validity. Besides, a personal data sheet was used to have information about some background factors of teacher educators.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The data was processed statistically to find out the results as per the objective of the study. The coefficient of correlation was computed using SPSS. The Table-1 reveals that the coefficient of correlation between Emotional Exhaustion (EE), Depersonalisation (DP) and Personal Accomplishment (PA) components of burnout among teacher educators of aided institutions and their perception of institutional climate is -0.23, -0.26 and 0.24 respectively. These values of correlation are statistically not-significant at 0.05 level.

Table -1
Burnout & Institutional Climate in grant-in-aid institutions

Type of institution	N	Coefficient of correlation 'r' between		
		EE & IC	DP&IC	PA&IC
Aided	46	-0.23NS	-0.26NS	0.24NS

NS p > 0.05 (Not-significant)

The results of the study reveal that burnout in teacher educators working in grant-in-aid institutions is independent of the institutional climate of the institution. It means institutional climate need not necessarily be the reason of burnout among teacher-educators. Burnout may be caused by factors other than institutional climate. Factors contributing to burnout in human service programmes can be found at three different levels of analysis: the individual, the work setting and the larger culture & society (Cherniss, 1980). Though in many cases the work setting factor is most important for burnout but other factors can't be ignored. Specific personal factors contributing to the experience of burnout may be genetic endowment, temperament, growth and development, physical health status, education and skills, training, motivation and interests, behaviour patterns, personality dynamics, mental health

status, work history and general life experiences ((Carroll & White, 1984). Age and sex are two other personal characteristics found to be associated with burnout.

The influence of the external environment on the work setting can't be overlooked. The nature of the community served by the programme has a strong impact on those aspects of the work setting that influence burnout. For example, the kind of stress experienced by staff may differ in rural and urban work settings. Local politics and attitudes of the community may influence job stress and burnout (Cherniss, 1980). The relationships between the educational institutions and other community organisations also influence burnout among staff.

CONCLUSION:

The results of the study do not validate the relationship between institutional climate and burnout in teacher-educators working there. It may be because of the fact that individual factors and social factors too affect burnout. As the teacher-educators of grant-in-aid institutions are well paid and they command social prestige, the institutional climate may not be the sole criterion of satisfaction they are getting from the profession. Besides, the teacher-educators are well educated and man of high learning, they may not bother much about the institutional climate.

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